

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF DIGITAL MARKETING ON CONSUMERS PURCHASING DECISIONS: A CONCEPTUAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT:

Change is natural in both humans and the universe. Change may happen for several reasons: due to the necessities of human beings or as a regular process of the universe. This change also happens due to the reason of innovation. To fulfil necessities, to make flexible or comfortable, to connect, or for any other reason on earth, it is happening continuously. Digitalization is also one of the modern-era requirements (may be change) to connect people. Using this digitalization in e-commerce will help to connect customers or consumers in a variety of formats.

Tremendous growth in e-Commerce directly influences digital marketing. In the traditional method, usually the consumer without touch or feel the product never goes for purchasing. Due to modern technology interference and a high boom in digital literacy, consumers take decisions within fingertip actions. In the present era, if a consumer wants to buy any product, first and foremost he will collect the information with the help of the internet. The "search" in the internet with the help of various online apps has made a major impact. This is what we call "digital marketing." In this paper we try to find out the impact of Digital marketing on consumer decision making based on various factors.

Key words: *Digital marketing, e-commerce, consumer, Search, technology and internet.*

INTRODUCTION:

Digital marketing means use various digital platforms to promote the product. Connect all the customers with the help of internet. Customers, who are all engaging in various online apps, seek their attention and convert them into potential buyers.

Objectives:

1. Define the terms "digital marketing" and "consumer purchase decision."
2. To know the impact of social media on the purchasing decisions of consumers.
3. To find out the various strategies of digital marketing to attract consumers.

Research questions:

1. Does digital marketing help consumers make purchasing decisions?
2. Is digital marketing effective and efficient?
3. Do customers' purchasing decisions benefit from digital marketing?

Research methodology:

Though it is a conceptual study, we are using secondary data, to find out the impact.

DIGITAL MARKETING:

Digital marketing is a form of direct marketing which links consumers with sellers electronically using interactive technologies like emails, websites, online forums and

newsgroups, interactive television, mobile communications etcetera (Kotler and Armstrong, 2009).

Digital marketing elevates marketing activities. It reduces the time it takes for a particular person to choose a particular product. He can compare, converse, or make queries. A marketer with a large number of opportunities to exhibit in front of customers can present the product with a variety of ideas.

PURCHASING DECISION:

At the time of purchase, the purchaser makes purchasing decisions, whether knowingly or unknowingly. For example:- Mr.'A' wishes to purchase a specific item, such as a note book. He has lots of confusion between notebooks. Which one he would like to buy? At that time, he finalised the two products, which had good features, with the help of online apps. Within those two, he compares which one is good for him and, according to his usage, he may select one. The process happening during the purchase may be called the purchasing decision.

It is a mental atmosphere status that one may be aware of but not be able to identify, or may identify but unknowingly. It is accompanied by various reciprocal factors.

FACTORS INFLUENCE THE PURCHASING DECISION:

Various factors influence the purchasing decision. They may be divided into emotional and cognitive factors.

Emotional factors in the brain include happiness, sadness, trust or belief, anger, surprises, suspicion, and unknowing alliances. We are not able to recognise the emotional connectivity of our brains. Some things are easy to like, while others are difficult to like. If we forcefully try to attach it, it will not be acceptable. Emotional factors are those factors that unknowingly influence our brain and nervous system.

A hasty decision may also be made with regard to appealing colors, brightness, or any other aspect. It is not easily recognizable. Many purchases are made in this type of situation. These factors are not easily recognizable, but they have an impact on any purchasing decision.

Cognitive factors influence the logical brain, and with the help of mental analysis, you purchase the product. Consider the price of the product and its worthiness. Discounting the product other than the emotional aspect, we are thinking logically. do not make decisions based on excitement; rather, they base their decisions on the utilisation point of view.

INFLUENCE OF DIGITAL MARKETING TO THE MODERN WORLD:

The human memory has a very short lifespan. Preferences may change continuously. That is why remembering anything about any product is critical. This type of influence is common in digital marketing. Regular or continuous connections with the modern world are at the tip of the finger; regular pop-ups, messages, mail, flyers, blinking ads, or any other medium of marketing are hunting continuously. Whichever products they make dominant with their promotion, those products are easily sustained in the open market.

Due to the influence of digital literacy, even the average person can easily access the product. A kid can make a purchase using online shopping. Traditional banners and hand flyers are almost extinct in the present era. The digital medium has a lot of influence on the decision to purchase a product. For example, if any person wants to purchase a mobile phone, he will not directly go and purchase the product. Before making a purchasing decision, he browses through various online purchasing apps, compares the products, and only then does he decide to purchase the product.

STRATEGIES USED BY DIGITAL MARKETERS TO ATTRACT CUSTOMERS:

Digital marketers are using various strategies popular of them are, Blog marketers, who are very firm with their activities because they know the target audience, are prominent among digital marketers who use various strategies. Which are the target audiences, and how do they attract customers with the help of content?

- 1) Make an advertisement on a specific platform like Meta (Facebook), YouTube, Twitter, LinkedIn, or any other popular social medium.
- 2) Create an offer with any educational resources. Make the content interesting. Attract customers through the use of knowledge.
- 3) Use SEO (search engine optimization) and major keywords to keep people thinking about your products.
- 4) Podcasting is one of the vigorous media where one can easily connect with different kinds of customers.

DIGITAL PLATFORM FINDINGS & ANALYSIS:

- There are 92.27 million users in India in 2010, 302.36 million in 2015, 749.07 million in 2020, 845.68 million in 2021, and 932.22 users in 2022. It is increasing continuously from 92.97 million users to now 932.22 users. This is the biggest impact of the rise in digital marketing. (Source: Statista 2022)
- In 2015, there were 142.25 million social media users in India. 2019: 87 million; 2020: 518.92 million; 2021: 639.47 million; and 2022: 755.47 million. Using social media helps make advertisements and market the product through social media. (Source: Statista 2022)
- India has the largest e-commerce market, ranking eighth in the world. In the festive season, it increases vigorously. The year-over-year growth rate is 17%, as per the predictions. (Source: ecommercedb)
- In 2018, India had 110 million online customers. In 2019, there are 135 million online users, 150 million in 2020, and 190 million in 2021 as a result of the pandemic. (Source: Statista 2022)
- 83% of total online users are using Smartphone's to buy products. That is why pop-up ads are becoming more popular; they make it easier for marketers to reach customers. (Source: Statista 2022)

CONCLUSION:

The digital platform is a growing platform. Customers want to buy their products online. Brighten colours, designs, and offers, it attracts consumers. Online marketing is growing like crazy, thanks to increases in digital literacy, digital India, the pandemic, demonetization in India, and consumers' social media habits. Suffering and searching are becoming popular words among buyers. Only customers are likely to buy a product after comparing and analysing it on various platforms.

Due increases in customers using internet it extends the hands of digital marketing. That's why digital marketing made a major impact on customers. It helps to remember the products continuously. It creates both logical and emotional mindsets. It made a vigorous impact on marketing activities.

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